

DEVELOPMENT OF NON-WOVEN BIOFIBRE MATS FOR COMPOSITE REINFORCEMENT

Z.C. Yu, M. Alcock, E. Rothwell, S. McKay
Composites Innovation Centre
300-78 Innovation Drive, Winnipeg, Canada R3T 6C2
zyu@compositesinnovation.ca

ABSTRACT

Non-woven bio-fibre mats were successfully developed for composite reinforcement using fibres extracted from flax and hemp grown and cultivated in Canada. The mats were consolidated by needlepunching, thermal bonding and in some cases no bonding at all. A small percentage of a polyester fibre that could be melted at low temperature was used as a binder in some of the mats. Three matting methods: scan-feed, wet-lay and air-lay were used. The quality of the mats was influenced by contaminants introduced in the fibre decortication processes. The flexural moduli of the bio-fibre composites were close to the modulus of E-glass chop strand mat composites. The air-lay hemp mat provided the best overall mechanical performance of the composites and displayed potential in manufacturing bus components.

Keywords: Biofibre, Non-woven, Reinforcement, Composites, Low cost.

INTRODUCTION

As a renewable material, biofibres meet the call for the reduction of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions. The “green” fibres have or are going to become an alternative to glass fibres in many fields of application. Automotive and mass transportation industries have shown increased interests in biofibres because of low density, ease of handling, recycling capabilities and low price. Biofibres may come from naturally grown flax, hemp, jute, sisal, abaca, palm, cotton, coir, kapok and others. The non-wood biofibres that are grown in North America are primarily sourced from flax and hemp. The fibres have comparable tensile modulus to E-glass fibre and suitable tensile strengths. However, the non-homogeneity of the fibres and presence of contaminants, such as shive, are a commonly perceived problem. To incorporate biofibres into resin infusion applications, the fibres needed to be processed into a mat form suitable for handling in a composite environment. Engineered mats consisting of short and randomly oriented fibres were selected because of the ease of production as compared with woven materials and based on the target application of replacing chopped strand glass mat.

This paper describes a part of Composites Innovation Centre’s efforts in developing low cost biofibre mats as composite reinforcement to be used in liquid resin moulding. Non-woven biofibre mats were successfully developed using flax and hemp grown in

Canada. Various mat features were assessed and mechanical performance of the mat reinforced composites was evaluated.

NON-WOVEN BIOFIBRE MATS

The non-woven mats were expected to contain flax, hemp or a blend of flax and hemp fibres. In most cases a small percentage of a polyester fibre that could be melted at low temperature was used as a binder. Three matting methods: scan-feed, wet-lay and air-lay were used. The biofibres used to produce the mat had a target mean length of 5cm.

Scan feed (or chute feed) is a mat manufacturing process which produces a thick, even layer of fibres through the use of baffles. The layers of fibres were deposited onto a moving conveyor which created an even and continuous layer of fibres ready for subsequent bonding methods. The bonding methods used on the scan feed samples in these assessments were needlepunched and in some cases additional thermal bonding through a calendar was utilized. The thickness of mat which this process is designed to produce had a higher areal weight than desired for a liquid moulding application. By reducing the mat thickness with the scan feed method, the ability for the baffles to produce a consistent layer was compromised. This led to an uneven distribution of fibres in the final product.

The wet-lay process used water to distribute the fibres. Fibres were circulated in a vat of water and mixed/distributed in the water using a propeller. The fibre and water mixture was circulated into a tank with a screen conveyor. The fibre was deposited on the surface of the screen while the water was allowed to flow through. By controlling the flow of the water, the thickness of the fibres deposited on the screen could be influenced. The material on the conveyor was collected as a continuous roll and the material was dried.

The air-lay process used a single roller with teeth to collect a sample of fibre. The unit pulled the fibres off the roller pneumatically and the fibres were dispersed into a web via airflow. The layers produced by the air-lay process are thin and need to be stacked prior to bonding. Methods used to consolidate the mat were needlepunching and thermal bonding. Unlike in the previous mat manufacturing methods, the thermal bonding did not use a calendar to apply heat and pressure; only heat was used.

In collaboration with Philadelphia University (Philadelphia, PA) and North Carolina State University (Raleigh, NC), Composites Innovation Centre (Canada) successfully manufactured a variety of the biofibre mats consisting of individual or blended fibre types through combinations of the mat forming and binding methods. Table 1 lists 10 mats which were selected for further assessments.

Table 1: Lists of Mat Composition and Processing Methods

Mat #	Process			Fibre Type (% by Weight)		
	Mat	Bonding	Bonding 2	Hemp	Flax	CoPoly
2A	Scan Feed	Needlepunch	-	50	50	-
2B	Scan Feed	Needlepunch	-	47.5	47.5	5
2C	Scan Feed	Needlepunch	Calendar	-	95	5
2D	Wet-Lay	Dry	-	90	-	10
2E	Wet-Lay	Dry	-	47.5	47.5	5
2F	Wet-Lay	Dry	-	95	-	5
2H	Air-Lay	Needlepunch	-	-	90	10
2I	Air-Lay	Thermal Bond	-	90	-	10
2J	Air-Lay	Needlepunch	-	-	100	-
2K	Air-Lay	Needlepunch	-	100	-	-

FEATURES OF THE BIOFIBRE MATS

The scan feed mats had a slight orientation pattern due to the flow of fibres during the needlepunching and compaction process. The mats were generally more dense and thicker than their glass counterparts. Spots where the fibre volume density was less than adjacent areas could be found scattered through the roll. Track lines, punched by needles, indicated the mat feeding direction. The mat blended with 5% by weight of polyester fibres formed white clusters reflecting that the blending of the polyester binder was not thorough enough to achieve an even consistency.

Mat (Blended Hemp and Flax Fibres)

Mat (95% Flax Fibres)

Figure 1 Scan-Feed Mat

Due to tangling issues in the water tank, fibres processed using the wet-lay system were reduced from the target length of 5cm to between 1cm and 2.5cm prior to wet forming. Wet-lay mats had loosely dispersed fibres which formed a thin layer with a texture similar to tissue, or un-bleached recycled paper. The mats were very fragile and some areas lacked fibres. The mats did not use a binder; fibres were held together by frictional

force. Due to some irregularities during processing, the mats were not consistent in fibre distribution across the width of the roll. However, this shortage could be compensated by purposely overlapping two or more layers of the mat to fill the regions deficient in fibres (Figure 2).

Single Wet-lay Mat Layer

Overlapped Wet-lay Mats

Figure 2 Wet-Lay Mat

The air-lay mat samples did not consist of a blended mix of flax and hemp fibres. The mats looked lofty and porous. Punctures were occasionally visible on the surface, caused by the needlepunching process. Polyester bonded mats did not show visible white clumps as observed in scan-feed mats.

Figure 3 Air-lay Mats

All the air-lay hemp mats felt clean, soft, and silky; the fibres were uniformly distributed and randomly oriented.

Comparing the flax and hemp mats overall, the flax mats felt stiff and rough. Shives and other contaminants could be found on each of flax mats. Irregular fibre distribution as well as agglomeration was found in many of these mats.

Figure 4 Air-lay 100% Flax Mat

Fibre agglomeration was a consistent problem in the mats containing flax fibres and may have been a significant cause of voids and fibre deficient areas in the composite trials. Shives and other contaminants were found at the nuclei of the agglomerated fibres and may have contributed to their development. The agglomeration effect may not be solely attributable to flax and not hemp, but there may be a relation to the different fibre extraction techniques chosen for the flax and hemp.

Permeability of the biofibre mats were experimentally determined using typical VARTM method (Figure 5). There was not a clear indication that any mat forming method was consistently superior to the other matting methods.

Figure 5 Permeability Test Results

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITES

Biofibre composite panels were manufactured through a vacuum assisted RTM process. To minimize the panel thickness variance, a rigid mould was developed for mat compaction. Hydropel R037-YDF-40, which has found to be the most compatible with

flax fibre when compared to resins of similar performance [1], was selected as the resin for the matrix. The vinyl ester resin was catalyzed by 2% of Luperox DDM9 before infusion. The fibre volume fraction of all biofibre composite panels was controlled at 20%.

Multiple layers were required for preforming wet-lay mats. The multiple layer structure reduced the irregularities of the preform by averaging the irregularities between the layers. The compaction in the manufacturing process further reduced voids in the resulting composite panels. The wet-lay composites contained fewer voids than both the scan-feed and the air-lay mat composites. However, as a mat form, wet-lay mat was flimsy, fragile and thus lacked processability.

In general, the scan-feed mats did not require multiple layer preforming. The dense mats were found to be stiff and did not easily conform to the tooling surface. The resin infiltration time was comparatively longer than that observed on other mats.

Comparatively, air-lay mats were more uniform than other mats. The mats were soft and easy to conform to tooling surface offering a good balance of efficiency, quality and productivity; however, the pressure needed to achieve compaction was greater with the air-lay than the wet-lay mats.

The mechanical properties of the biofibre composites were assessed by tension, flexure, short beam shear and Izod impact tests. All tests were conducted at room temperature in accordance with the respective test standards: ASTM D638, D790, D2344 and D4812. Because of the possible material anisotropy, scan-feed mat samples were tested along directions parallel and transverse to the mat feeding direction and labelled by letter P for parallel or T for transverse. Tension and flexure test results are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Tensile and Flexural Test Results of the Biofibre Composites

Mat#	Tension			Flexure	
	Strength MPa	Modulus Gpa	Elongation %	Strength MPa	Modulus GPa
2K	48.3	5.0	1.2	80.0	6.1
2I	39.4	4.5	1.2	64.6	5.2
2D	38.0	4.4	1.1	65.3	5.6
2F	37.7	4.5	1.0	70.1	5.7
2E	34.0	4.1	1.0	58.6	4.9
2B-P	32.9	3.9	1.0	55.4	4.6
2A-P	32.8	4.4	1.0	64.3	5.2
2B-T	31.3	3.8	1.0	60.4	4.6
2J	30.2	4.0	1.0	65.9	4.8
2H	28.7	3.8	0.9	53.2	4.5
2C-T	26.1	3.6	0.9	63.1	4.8
2C-P	25.0	3.7	0.8	49.9	4.9
2A-T	25.0	3.9	0.8	58.0	4.7

All hemp fibre composites illustrated a higher strength and modulus than their flax fibre counterparts regardless of the matting method. The composites, which were made using

flax and hemp blends, presented intermediate values. This phenomenon may be attributed primarily to the irregularity of the flax mats and the noticeable fibre agglomeration. The inconsistencies could be an important cause of voids and resin pockets in the manufactured composites and thus negatively impacted the strength and modulus properties.

The air-lay hemp mat composites were above average performers in both strength and modulus values. The needlepunch 100% hemp mat performed better than thermal-bonded 90% hemp mat in both tension and flexure, and provided the maximum strength and modulus among all the mats tested. Similar to air-lay hemp mat composites, the air-lay 100% flax mat composites also showed tensile and flexure properties better than air-lay 90% flax mat composites, although their strength and modulus were below the average found for the biofibre mat composites as a whole.

Table 3 lists the design performance tolerances that are allowable for bus components [4] and the mechanical properties of hand lay-up E-glass chop strand mat (csm) composites. It is obvious that all hemp fibre composites, regardless of the matting methods, provide a flexure modulus equal or above the design allowable but below the E-glass csm composites.

Table 3: Design Allowable of Bus Components, E-Glass Chop Strand Mat and Hemp mat Composites Properties

Mat	Tension		Flexure	
	Strength MPa	Modulus Gpa	Strength Mpa	Modulus Gpa
Design allowable	82.7	7.6	142	5.2
E-glass csm	138	10.3	221	8.5
Hemp mat (2K)	48.3	5.0	80.0	6.1

The wet-lay mat composites consistently delivered higher short beam shear strength (Figure 6), reflecting the superior quality over other composite panels.

Figure 6 Short Beam Shear Test Results

Air-lay hemp mats were the strong competitor to their wet-lay counterparts. The air-lay 100% hemp composites delivered a very close SBS strength to the wet-lay 95% hemp mat composites which presented the highest SBS strength. As in the tension and flexure, high hemp concentration resulted in a higher SBS strength for both air-lay and wet-lay hemp mat composites.

The air-lay 100% flax mat composites presented the lowest SBS strength among the all biofibre mat composites tested and it was suspected that this corresponds to a high level of contamination from the shives and fibre agglomeration as the SBS strength of all the mats manufactured with a flax blend showed decreased performance in comparison to hemp mat made using the same process.

The material anisotropy of scan-feed mats was apparent when the composite panels were tested for impact performance. The impact strength (Figure 7) was clearly directionally dependent for all scan-feed composites. The parallel direction delivered a higher strength than the transverse direction. The scanfeed-needlepunch-calendar 95% flax mat composites had the highest impact strength (6.5kJ/m) in the parallel direction. However, the strength in transverse direction of the scan-feed mat composites was below or at the average of the all biofibre mat composites tested.

The wet-lay mat composites generally showed average impact strength. Again, the air-lay 100% hemp mat composite panel demonstrated itself as a strong competitor in the impact by showing the second highest impact strength (5.7kJ/m²).

Figure 7 Impact Strength

CONCLUSION

Low cost biofibre mats were successfully developed through different manufacturing methods. While wet lay and scan feed mats demonstrated specific advantages, the air-lay hemp mat reinforced composites delivered the best overall performance in the mechanical evaluations conducted. The developed mats are potentially applicable in making bus components.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank the Department of Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada and Schweitzer-Mauduit Canada Inc. for their support of this project.

References

1. Komus and S. Meatherall, Report No. 07-020-08-R02, Assessment of Thermoset Resin compatibility with Flax Fibers for Composite Panels Composites Innovation Centre, March 2008.
2. M. Alcock and S.Boyko, Report No. 06-020-03-R01, Flax Fibre Mat Assessment. Composites Innovation Centre, June 2007
3. M. Alcock and S.Boyko, Report No. 06-020-03-R03 Natural Fibre Mat for Reinforcing Thermoset Composite Parts – Mat Manufacturing Reportt. Composites Innovation Centre, June 2008.
4. Shawna Boyko, Project No. 06-020-02-R03, BioComposites Collaboration Project Motor Coach Industry Parts. Composites Innovation Centre, May 2007